

Chalcones X: Syntheses of Naphthalene Chalcone Analogues

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A number of naphthalene analogues of chalcone have been synthesised to study their antimicrobial activity against gram positive (*S. aureus*) and gram negative (*E. coli*) bacteria¹⁻⁵. They were synthesised through the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone and aryl aldehydes² in presence of alcoholic potash to yield the naphthyl styryl ketones. The condensation with chloro- and methoxy-benzaldehydes were effected at room temperature for 6-8 hr; for methyl-benzaldehydes at room temperature for 30-50 hr- and for the hydroxy benzaldehydes in cold for 7 days. The compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 1

R	M.P. °C† of		Yield %	Halochromism with Conc. H ₂ SO ₄
	Chalcone	2 : 4-DNP		
3-OH	211	255	36	brown
2-Cl	176	—	87	crimson red
3-Cl	121	258	81	blood-red
4-Cl	138	267(dec)	85	blood-red
2-Me	176	268	63	orange
3-Me	88	241	57	pink
4-Me	133	—	60	chocolate
2-MeO	122	252	62	purple
3-MeO	138	262	55	brown
3-MeO-4-OH-5-Br**	131	—	57	orange
2,3-(MeO) ₂	144	208	64	brown
3,4-(MeO) ₂	148	233	66	violet
4-NMe ₂ **	93	—	54	blood-red
2-OH-5,6-benzo	81	217	38	purple

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† All melting points are uncorrected.

** Crystallised from ethyl acetate.

The compounds gave crystalline orange to red 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, and vivid colours on melting with concentrated sulphuric acid. Elemental analyses of C, H and N for the ketones and the dinitrophenylhydrazones were within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the expected value.

The results of antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* were not encouraging.

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